

Verification

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- ✓ Issued using Credly
- ✓ Issued to Manohar Karanth P D
- ✓ Accepted on October 30, 2021
- ✓ Last Updated April 07, 2024
- ✓ **VERIFIED**

This badge was issued
Expires on October 2

✓ Verified

Celebrate

g – Specialty

AWS machine learning (ML)
ploy ML models using the AWS
using either pretrained models or